

Neutrosophic Doubt Fuzzy Bi-ideal of BS-Algebras

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Abstract. In this research paper, our aim is to introduce the new concept of neutrosophic doubt fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebras as an extension of doubt fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebras and investigated its algebraic nature. Neutrosophic doubt fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebras is also applied in Cartesian product. Finally, we also provide the homomorphic behaviour of Neutrosophic doubt fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebras.

Keywords: BS-algebras, Neutrosophic doubt fuzzy bi-ideal, Homomorphism.

1. Introduction

The fuzzy subsets was first introduced by L.A.Zadeh[8]. In 1966, Imai and Iseki gave the idea of BCK-algebras and BCI-algebras[3]. J.Negggers and H.S. Kim initiated the notion of B-algebras[4] which is a generalisation of BCK-algebras. We launched the notion of BS-algebras which is a generalisation of B-algebras and established the notion of Doubt fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebras[1]. We also innovated the notion of Neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebras[2]. F. Smarandache[5] extented the concept of fuzzy logic to neutrosophic logic which includes indeterminacy. Neutrosophic set theory played a major role in decision making problem, medical diagnosis, robotics, image processing, etc.

The main objective of this paper is to putforth the notion of Neutrosophic Doubt Fuzzy Bi-ideal(NDFB) of BS-algebras and studied their algebraic properties. We obtained the product of neutrosophic doubt fuzzy bi-ideal for BS-algebras. Finally, we studied how to deal with homomorphism of neutrosophic doubt fuzzy bi-ideal for BS-algebras.

2. Preliminaries:

In this Section, some basic definitions are given that are necessary for this paper. Throughout this paper, let \mathfrak{B} denotes BS-algebra.

Definition 2.1 [1] A set BS-algebra $\mathfrak{B} \neq \emptyset$ with 1 as constant and * as binary operation satisfying the following axioms

- (i) $\alpha * \alpha = 1$
- (ii) $\alpha * 1 = \alpha$
- (iii) $(\alpha * \beta) * \gamma = \alpha * (\gamma * (1 * \beta)) \forall \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathfrak{B}$

Definition 2.2 A fuzzy subset F of \mathfrak{B} is called the fuzzy ideal of \mathfrak{B} if it satisfies

- (i) $F(1) \geq F(\alpha)$
- (ii) $F(\beta) \geq \{F(\alpha) \wedge F(\beta * \alpha)\} \forall \alpha, \beta \in \mathfrak{B}$

Definition 2.3 [1] A fuzzy subset F of \mathfrak{B} is called the fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B} if it satisfies

- (i) $F(1) \geq F(\alpha)$
- (ii) $F(\beta * \gamma) \geq \{F(\alpha) \wedge F(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma))\} \forall \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathfrak{B}$

Definition 2.4 A fuzzy set F of \mathfrak{B} is called the doubt fuzzy ideal of \mathfrak{B} if it satisfies

- (i) $F(1) \leq F(\alpha)$
- (ii) $F(\beta) \leq \{F(\alpha) \vee F(\beta * \alpha)\} \forall \alpha, \beta \in \mathfrak{B}$

Definition 2.5 [1] A fuzzy set F of \mathfrak{B} is called the Doubt Fuzzy Bi-ideal (DF) of \mathfrak{B} if it satisfies

- (i) $F(1) \leq F(\alpha)$
- (ii) $F(\beta * \gamma) \leq \{F(\alpha) \vee F(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma))\} \forall \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathfrak{B}$

Example 2.6 [1] Let $\mathfrak{B} = \{1, u, v, w\}$ be the set with the following Cayley table

*	1	u	v	w
1	1	u	v	w
u	u	1	w	v
v	v	w	1	u
w	w	v	u	1

Then $(\mathfrak{B}, *, 1)$ is a BS-algebra. Then the fuzzy set $F: \mathfrak{B} \rightarrow [0,1]$ is defined by $F(1) = F(u) = 0.7$ and $F(v) = F(w) = 0.9$, which is a Doubt Fuzzy (DF) bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B} .

Definition 2.7 [6] A Neutrosophic fuzzy set \mathcal{N} on the Universe of discourse X characterised by a truth membership function $\tau_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha)$, an indeterminacy function $\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha)$ and a falsity membership function $f_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha)$ is defined as $\mathcal{N} = \{\langle \alpha, \tau_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha), \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha), f_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha) \rangle : \alpha \in X\}$ where $\tau_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}, f_{\mathcal{N}} : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $0 \leq \tau_{\mathcal{N}} + \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}} + f_{\mathcal{N}} \leq 3$

Definition 2.8 [6] Let \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} be the two neutrosophic fuzzy set of X. Then $\alpha \in X$

i) $\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N} = \{ \langle \alpha, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(\alpha), \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(\alpha), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(\alpha) \rangle \}$, where

$$\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(\alpha) = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha)); \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(\alpha) = (\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{M}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha)); \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(\alpha) = (\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha))$$

ii) $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N} = \{ \langle \alpha, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(\alpha), \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(\alpha), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(\alpha) \rangle \}$, where

$$\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(\alpha) = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha)); \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(\alpha) = (\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{M}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha)); \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(\alpha) = (\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha))$$

Definition 2.9 A Neutrosophic Fuzzy Set \mathcal{N} of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B} is called the Neutrosophic Fuzzy Ideal of \mathfrak{B} if $\forall a, \beta, \gamma \in \mathfrak{B}$

(i) $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(1) \geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha); \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(1) \leq \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha); \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(1) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha);$

(ii) $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(\beta) \geq \{ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(\beta^* \alpha) \};$

$$\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(\beta) \leq \{ \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(\beta^* \alpha) \};$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(\beta) \leq \{ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(\beta^* \alpha) \}$$

Definition 2.10 [2] A Neutrosophic fuzzy set \mathcal{N} of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B} is called the Neutrosophic Fuzzy Bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B} if $\forall a, \beta, \gamma \in \mathfrak{B}$

(i) $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(1) \geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha); \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(1) \leq \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha); \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(1) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha);$

(ii) $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(\beta^* \gamma) \geq \{ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha^* (\beta^* \gamma)) \};$

$$\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(\beta^* \gamma) \leq \{ \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha^* (\beta^* \gamma)) \};$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(\beta^* \gamma) \leq \{ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(\alpha^* (\beta^* \gamma)) \}$$

Definition 2.11 A Neutrosophic fuzzy set \mathcal{D} of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B} is called the Neutrosophic Doubt Fuzzy Ideal of \mathfrak{B} if $\forall a, \beta, \gamma \in \mathfrak{B}$

(i) $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(1) \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha); \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(1) \geq \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha); \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(1) \geq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha);$

(ii) $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta) \leq \{ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta^* \alpha) \};$

$$\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta) \geq \{ \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta^* \alpha) \};$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta) \geq \{ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta^* \alpha) \}$$

3. NEUTROSOPHIC DOUBT FUZZY BI-IDEAL (NDFB) OF BS-ALGEBRAS

In this Section, the concept of doubt fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B} can be extended to Neutrosophic doubt fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B} . We proved that the union of two NDFB of \mathfrak{B} is again a NDFB of \mathfrak{B} . We also proved that the intersection of two NDFB of \mathfrak{B} is again a NDFB of \mathfrak{B} .

Definition 3.1 A Neutrosophic fuzzy set \mathcal{D} of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B} is called the Neutrosophic Doubt Fuzzy Bi-ideal (NDFB) of \mathfrak{B} if $\forall a, \beta, \gamma \in \mathfrak{B}$

(\mathcal{D}_1) $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(1) \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha); \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(1) \geq \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha); \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(1) \geq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha);$

(\mathcal{D}_2) $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta^* \gamma) \leq \{ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^* (\beta^* \gamma)) \};$

$$\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta^* \gamma) \geq \{ \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^* (\beta^* \gamma)) \};$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta^* \gamma) \geq \{ \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^* (\beta^* \gamma)) \}$$

Theorem 3.2 Let \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} be two NDFB of \mathfrak{B} . Then $\mathcal{C} \cup \mathcal{D}$ is a NDFB of \mathfrak{B} .

Proof

Let \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} be two NDFB of \mathfrak{B} . For any $a, \beta, \gamma \in \mathfrak{B}$

i) $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \cup \mathcal{D}}(1) = \{ \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(1) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(1) \}$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \{\mathcal{T}_c(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_d(\alpha)\} \\ &= \mathcal{T}_{c \cup d}(\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{c \cup d}(1) \leq \mathcal{T}_{c \cup d}(\alpha)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \mathcal{J}_{c \cup d}(1) &= \{\mathcal{J}_c(1) \wedge \mathcal{J}_d(1)\} \\ &\geq \{\mathcal{J}_c(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_d(\alpha)\} \\ &= \mathcal{J}_{c \cup d}(\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{J}_{c \cup d}(1) \geq \mathcal{J}_{c \cup d}(\alpha)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \mathcal{F}_{c \cup d}(1) &= \{\mathcal{F}_c(1) \wedge \mathcal{F}_d(1)\} \\ &\geq \{\mathcal{F}_c(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{F}_d(\alpha)\} \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{c \cup d}(\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{F}_{c \cup d}(1) \geq \mathcal{F}_{c \cup d}(\alpha)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii) } \mathcal{T}_{c \cup d}(\beta^* \gamma) &= \{\mathcal{T}_c(\beta^* \gamma) \vee \mathcal{T}_d(\beta^* \gamma)\} \\ &\leq \{\{\mathcal{T}_c(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_c(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\} \vee \{\mathcal{T}_d(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_d(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\}\} \\ &= \{\{\mathcal{T}_c(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_d(\alpha)\} \vee \{\mathcal{T}_c(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma)) \vee \mathcal{T}_d(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\}\} \\ &= \{\mathcal{T}_{c \cup d}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{c \cup d}(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{c \cup d}(\beta^* \gamma) \leq \{\mathcal{T}_{c \cup d}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{c \cup d}(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \mathcal{J}_{c \cup d}(\beta^* \gamma) &= \{\mathcal{J}_c(\beta^* \gamma) \wedge \mathcal{J}_d(\beta^* \gamma)\} \\ &\geq \{\{\mathcal{J}_c(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_c(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\} \wedge \{\mathcal{J}_d(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_d(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\}\} \\ &= \{\{\mathcal{J}_c(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_d(\alpha)\} \wedge \{\mathcal{J}_c(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma)) \wedge \mathcal{J}_d(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\}\} \\ &= \{\mathcal{J}_{c \cup d}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{c \cup d}(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{J}_{c \cup d}(\beta^* \gamma) \geq \{\mathcal{J}_{c \cup d}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{c \cup d}(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \mathcal{F}_{c \cup d}(\beta^* \gamma) &= \{\mathcal{F}_c(\beta^* \gamma) \wedge \mathcal{F}_d(\beta^* \gamma)\} \\ &\geq \{\{\mathcal{F}_c(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{F}_c(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\} \wedge \{\mathcal{F}_d(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{F}_d(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\}\} \\ &= \{\{\mathcal{F}_c(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{F}_d(\alpha)\} \wedge \{\mathcal{F}_c(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma)) \wedge \mathcal{F}_d(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\}\} \\ &= \{\mathcal{F}_{c \cup d}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{c \cup d}(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{F}_{c \cup d}(\beta^* \gamma) \geq \{\mathcal{F}_{c \cup d}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{c \cup d}(\alpha^*(\beta^* \gamma))\}$

Hence, $c \cup d$ is a NDFB of \mathfrak{B}

Theorem 3.3 Let c and d be two NDFB of \mathfrak{B} . Then $c \cap d$ is a NDFB of \mathfrak{B} .

Proof

Let c and d be two NDFB of \mathfrak{B} . For any $a, \beta, \gamma \in \mathfrak{B}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i) } \mathcal{T}_{c \cap d}(1) &= \{\mathcal{T}_c(1) \wedge \mathcal{T}_d(1)\} \\ &\leq \{\mathcal{T}_c(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{T}_d(\alpha)\} \\ &= \mathcal{T}_{c \cap d}(\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{c \cap d}(1) \leq \mathcal{T}_{c \cap d}(\alpha)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \mathcal{J}_{c \cap d}(1) &= \{\mathcal{J}_c(1) \vee \mathcal{J}_d(1)\} \\ &\geq \{\mathcal{J}_c(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{J}_d(\alpha)\} \\ &= \mathcal{J}_{c \cap d}(\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{J}_{c \cap d}(1) \geq \mathcal{J}_{c \cap d}(\alpha)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \mathcal{F}_{c \cap d}(1) &= \{\mathcal{F}_c(1) \vee \mathcal{F}_d(1)\} \\ &\geq \{\mathcal{F}_c(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{F}_d(\alpha)\} \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{c \cap d}(\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{F}_{c \cap d}(1) \geq \mathcal{F}_{c \cap d}(\alpha)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(ii) } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\beta^*\gamma) &= \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(\beta^*\gamma) \wedge \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta^*\gamma)\} \\
 &\leq \{\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\} \wedge \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\}\} \\
 &= \{\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)\} \vee \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma)) \wedge \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\}\} \\
 &= \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\beta^*\gamma) \leq \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{and } \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\beta^*\gamma) &= \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(\beta^*\gamma) \vee \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta^*\gamma)\} \\
 &\geq \{\{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\} \vee \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\}\} \\
 &= \{\{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)\} \wedge \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma)) \vee \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\}\} \\
 &= \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\beta^*\gamma) \geq \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\}$

Similarly, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\beta^*\gamma) \geq \{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\}$

Hence, $\mathcal{C}\cap\mathcal{D}$ is a NDFB of \mathfrak{B}

Corollary 3.4 Let $\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2, \dots, \mathcal{D}_n$ are NDFB of \mathfrak{B} , then $\mathcal{D} = \bigcap_{i=1}^n \mathcal{D}_i$ is also a NDFB of \mathfrak{B}

Proof

Straight forward using theorem 3.3

Lemma 3.5 For all $s, t \in I$ and i be any positive integer, if $s = t$, then

- i) $s^i \leq t^i$
- ii) $[(s \wedge t)]^i = (s^i \wedge t^i)$
- iii) $[(s \vee t)]^i = (s^i \vee t^i)$

Theorem 3.6 Let \mathcal{D} be a NDFB of \mathfrak{B} , then $\mathcal{D}^i = \{\langle \alpha, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha), \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha) \rangle : \alpha \in \mathfrak{B}\}$ is a NDFB of \mathfrak{B}^i , where i is any positive integer and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha) = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))^i, \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha) = (\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))^i, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha) = (\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))^i$

Proof

Let \mathcal{D} be a NDFB of \mathfrak{B} . For any $a, \beta, \gamma \in \mathfrak{B}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{i) } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(1) &= (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(1))^i \\
 &\leq (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))^i \\
 &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(1) \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{and } \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(1) &= (\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(1))^i \\
 &\geq (\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))^i \\
 &= \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(1) \geq \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{and } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(1) &= (\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(1))^i \\
 &\geq (\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))^i \\
 &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(1) \geq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{ii) } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\beta^*\gamma) &= (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta^*\gamma))^i \\
 &\leq [\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\}]^i \\
 &= \{[\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)]^i \vee [\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))]^i\} \\
 &= \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\beta^*\gamma) \leq \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha^*(\beta^*\gamma))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\beta * \gamma) &= (\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta * \gamma))^i \\ &\geq [\{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma))\}]^i \\ &= \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)\}^i \wedge \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma))\}^i \\ &= \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\beta * \gamma) \geq \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma))\}$

Similarly, we can prove that $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\beta * \gamma) \geq \{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}^i}(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma))\}$

Hence \mathcal{D}^i is a NDFB of \mathfrak{B}^i

4. PRODUCT OF NEUTROSOPHIC DOUBT FUZZY BI IDEAL OF BS-ALGEBRAS

In this section, the product of NDFB of \mathfrak{B} are defined and corresponding theorems are investigated.

Definition 4.1 Let \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} be two neutrosophic doubt fuzzy subsets of \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 respectively.

Then the direct product of neutrosophic doubt fuzzy subsets of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 is defined by

$\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}: \mathfrak{B}_1 \times \mathfrak{B}_2 \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that

$\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D} = \{ \langle (\alpha, \beta), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha, \beta), \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha, \beta), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha, \beta) \rangle : \alpha \in \mathfrak{B}_1, \beta \in \mathfrak{B}_2 \}$, where

$\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha, \beta) = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta)); \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha, \beta) = (\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta)); \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha, \beta) = (\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta))$

Definition 4.2 Let \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} be two neutrosophic doubt fuzzy subsets of \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 respectively. Then $\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}$ is a NDFB of $\mathfrak{B}_1 \times \mathfrak{B}_2$ if it satisfies the following conditions

- i) $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(1,1) \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2); \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(1,1) \geq \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2); \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(1,1) \geq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2);$
- ii) $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}((\beta_1, \beta_2)^* (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)) \leq \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}((\alpha_1, \alpha_2)^* ((\beta_1, \beta_2)^* (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)))\};$
 $\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}((\beta_1, \beta_2)^* (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)) \geq \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}((\alpha_1, \alpha_2)^* ((\beta_1, \beta_2)^* (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)))\};$
 $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}((\beta_1, \beta_2)^* (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)) \geq \{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}((\alpha_1, \alpha_2)^* ((\beta_1, \beta_2)^* (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)))\}.$

Theorem 4.3 Let \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} be two NDFB of \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 respectively. Then $\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}$ is a NDFB of $\mathfrak{B}_1 \times \mathfrak{B}_2$

Proof

Let \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} be two NDFB of \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 respectively.

Let $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2), (\beta_1, \beta_2), (\gamma_1, \gamma_2) \in \mathfrak{B}_1 \times \mathfrak{B}_2$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i) We have } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(1,1) &= \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(1) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)\} \\ &\leq \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha_1) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2)\} \\ &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(1,1) \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(1,1) &= \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(1) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)\} \\ &\geq \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha_1) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2)\} \\ &= \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(1,1) \geq \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(1,1) &= \{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C}}(1) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)\} \\ &\geq \{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha_1) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2)\} \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(1,1) \geq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii) Then } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}((\beta_1, \beta_2)^* (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D}}(\beta_1 * \gamma_1, \beta_2 * \gamma_2) \\ &= \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(\beta_1 * \gamma_1) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_2 * \gamma_2)\} \\ &\leq [\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha_1) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha_1 * (\beta_1 * \gamma_1))\} \vee \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2 * (\beta_2 * \gamma_2))\}] \\ &= [\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha_1) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2)\} \vee \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha_1 * (\beta_1 * \gamma_1)) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2 * (\beta_2 * \gamma_2))\}] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1 * (\beta_1 * \gamma_1)), (\alpha_2 * (\beta_2 * \gamma_2))\} \\
 &= \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}((\alpha_1, \alpha_2) * ((\beta_1, \beta_2) * (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}((\beta_1, \beta_2) * (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)) \leq \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}((\alpha_1, \alpha_2) * ((\beta_1, \beta_2) * (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)))\}$

and $\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}((\beta_1, \beta_2) * (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)) = \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1 * \gamma_1, \beta_2 * \gamma_2)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(\beta_1 * \gamma_1) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_2 * \gamma_2)\} \\
 &\geq [\{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha_1) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha_1 * (\beta_1 * \gamma_1))\} \wedge \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2 * (\beta_2 * \gamma_2))\}] \\
 &= [\{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha_1) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2)\} \wedge \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}}(\alpha_1 * (\beta_1 * \gamma_1)) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2 * (\beta_2 * \gamma_2))\}] \\
 &= \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)\} \wedge \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1 * (\beta_1 * \gamma_1)) \wedge (\alpha_2 * (\beta_2 * \gamma_2))\} \\
 &= \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)\} \wedge \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}((\alpha_1, \alpha_2) * ((\beta_1, \beta_2) * (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}((\beta_1, \beta_2) * (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)) \geq \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}((\alpha_1, \alpha_2) * ((\beta_1, \beta_2) * (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)))\}$

Similarly we can easily prove that,

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}((\beta_1, \beta_2) * (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)) \geq \{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}}((\alpha_1, \alpha_2) * ((\beta_1, \beta_2) * (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)))\}$$

Hence $\mathcal{C}\mathcal{X}\mathcal{D}$ is a NDFB of $\mathfrak{B}_1 \times \mathfrak{B}_2$

5. HOMOMORPHISM OF NDFB OF \mathfrak{B}

In this section, the homomorphic behaviour of NDFB of \mathfrak{B} are defined and related theorems are discussed.

Definition 5.1 Let \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 be two BS-algebras and $h: \mathfrak{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}_2$ be a function.

i) If \mathcal{D} is a NDFB in \mathfrak{B}_2 , then the preimage of \mathcal{D} under h denoted by $h^{-1}(\mathcal{D})$ is the NDFB in \mathfrak{B}_1 is defined by $h^{-1}(\mathcal{D}) = \{<(\alpha), h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)), h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)), h^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))>: \alpha \in \mathfrak{B}\}$,

where $h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)) = \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha))$; $h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)) = \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha))$; $h^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha))$;

Theorem 5.2 Let $h: \mathfrak{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}_2$ be an epimorphism of BS-algebras if \mathcal{D} is a NDFB of \mathfrak{B}_2 , then the pre image of \mathcal{D} under h is also a NDFB of \mathfrak{B}_1 .

Proof

Let \mathcal{D} is a NDFB of \mathfrak{B}_2 . Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathfrak{B}_1$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Now, } h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(1)) \\
 &\leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha)) \\
 &= h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)) \leq h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{and } h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)) &= \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(1)) \\
 &\geq \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha)) \\
 &= h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)) \geq h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{and } h^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(1)) \\
 &\geq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha)) \\
 &= h^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $h^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)) \geq h^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{ii) Again, } h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta * \gamma)) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\beta * \gamma)) \\
 &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\beta) * h(\gamma)) \\
 &\leq \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha)) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha) * [h(\beta) * h(\gamma)])\} \\
 &= \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha)) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma)))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta * \gamma)) \leq \{h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)) \vee h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma)))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta * \gamma)) &= \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\beta * \gamma)) \\ &= \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\beta) * h(\gamma)) \\ &\geq \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha)) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha) * [h(\beta) * h(\gamma)])\} \\ &= \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha)) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma)))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta * \gamma)) \geq \{h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)) \wedge h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma)))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } h^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta * \gamma)) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\beta * \gamma)) \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\beta) * h(\gamma)) \\ &\geq \{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha)) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha) * [h(\beta) * h(\gamma)])\} \\ &= \{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha)) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma)))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $h^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta * \gamma)) \geq \{h^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)) \wedge h^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha * (\beta * \gamma)))\}$

Hence $h^{-1}(\mathcal{D})$ is a NDFB of \mathfrak{B}_1 .

Definition 5.3 [1] Let \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 be two BS-algebras $h: \mathfrak{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}_2$ be a homomorphism. Then $h(1) = 1$

Theorem 5.4 Let $h: \mathfrak{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}_2$ be a homomorphism of BS-algebras if \mathcal{D} is a NDFB of \mathfrak{B}_1 , then $h(\mathcal{D})$ is a NDFB of \mathfrak{B}_2 .

Proof

Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3 \in \mathfrak{B}_1$ and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 \in \mathfrak{B}_2$ such that $h(\alpha_1) = \beta_1, h(\alpha_2) = \beta_2, h(\alpha_3) = \beta_3$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_1)) \\ &= h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1)) \\ &\geq h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)) \\ &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(1)) \\ &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(1) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1) \geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1) &= \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_1)) \\ &= h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1)) \\ &\leq h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)) \\ &= \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(1)) \\ &= \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(1) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1) \leq \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1) &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_1)) \\ &= h^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1)) \\ &\leq h^{-1}(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)) \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(1)) \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(1) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(1)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii) Again, } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_2 * \beta_3) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_2) * h(\alpha_3)) \\ &= h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2 * \alpha_3)) \\ &\leq \{h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1)) \vee h^{-1}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1 * (\alpha_2 * \alpha_3)))\} \\ &= \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_1)) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_1 * (\alpha_2 * \alpha_3)))\} \\ &= \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_1)) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_1) * (h(\alpha_2) * h(\alpha_3)))\} \\ &= \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1 * (\beta_2 * \beta_3))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_2 * \beta_3) \leq \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1) \vee \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1 * (\beta_2 * \beta_3))\}$

And $\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_2 * \beta_3) = \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_2) * h(\alpha_3))$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_2 * \alpha_3)) \\
&\geq \{h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1)) \wedge h^{-1}(\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha_1 * (\alpha_2 * \alpha_3)))\} \\
&= \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_1)) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_1 * (\alpha_2 * \alpha_3)))\} \\
&= \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_1)) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(h(\alpha_1 * (h(\alpha_2) * h(\alpha_3))))\} \\
&= \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1 * (\beta_2 * \beta_3))\}
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_2 * \beta_3) \geq \{\mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1) \wedge \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1 * (\beta_2 * \beta_3))\}$

Similarly, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_2 * \beta_3) \geq \{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1) \wedge \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{D}}(\beta_1 * (\beta_2 * \beta_3))\}$

Hence $h(\mathcal{D})$ is a NDFB of \mathfrak{B}_2 .

Conclusion

In this research paper, the notion of Neutrosophic doubt fuzzy bi-ideal (NDFB) of BS-algebras \mathfrak{B} are introduced and studied their algebraic properties. We obtained the Cartesian product of neutrosophic doubt fuzzy bi-ideal(NDFB) for BS-algebras \mathfrak{B} . Finally, we studied how to deal with homomorphism in neutrosophic doubt fuzzy bi-ideal(NDFB) for BS-algebras \mathfrak{B} .

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References

1. Ayesha Parveen, P.; Himaya Jaleela Begum, M. Doubt Fuzzy Bi-ideal of BS-Algebras. Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research 2019, Vol.6(3), pp. 20-24.
2. Ayesha Parveen, P.; Himaya Jaleela Begum, M. Neutrosophic Fuzzy Bi-ideal of BS-Algebras. International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research 2023, Vol.11(2), pp. 3250-3254.
3. Himaya Jaleela Begum, M. ; Jeyalakshmi, S. On Anti Fuzzy Bi-ideals in near-rings. International Journal of Mathematics and Soft Computing 2015, Vol.5(2), pp. 75-82.
4. Imai, Y.; Iseki, K. On Axiom System of Propositional Calculi. 15 Proc.Japan Academy 1966, Vol. 42, pp. 19-22.
5. Neggers, J.; Kim, H.S. On B-algebras. Math. Vensik 2002, Vol.54, pp. 21-29.
6. Smarandache, F.; Neutrosophy, a new branch of Philosophy logic in multiple-valued logic. An international journal 2002, vol.8(3), pp. 297-384.
7. Smarandache, F.; Neutrosophy and Neutrosophic logic, First international Conference on Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Logic set, Probability and Statistics, University of New Mexico, Gallup, NM 87301, USA (2002)
8. Smarandache, F.; Neutrosophic set - a generalization of the Intuitionistic fuzzy sets, J. Pure Appl.Math 2005, vol.24, pp. 287-297
9. Zadeh, L.A.; Fuzzy sets Information and control 1965, 8, pp. 338-353.

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